

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATIONS AS WELL AS IN THE FAMILY TO TELL STORIES BY WATCHING THE PACE

Maziyayeva Muqaddasxon Esonovna

Master of Fergana State University,
Teacher of Fergana pedagogical college

muqaddasxonmaziyayeva@gmail.com

Annotation: This article covers the theoretical issues of teaching children to tell stories by watching the pace in the preschool organization as well as in the family. Then the issues of a positive approach to the cultivation of children's speech through stories were analyzed in preschool educational organizations.

Keywords: preschool education, family, children, speech, story, pace.

In national education, upbringing is carried out in a more connected way to education as well as in the family. Education-upbringing prepares our little ones for life, School Education, a meticulous formation of a sense of desire for knowledge. In children, little by little, the need arises to seek knowledge and, based on this need, they are spiritually developed. To the established lifestyle of pride forms in children such highly positive feelings as striving for the future, longing, resistance to affection, love for the Native Land, self-sacrifice, national pride, consequence, friendship, goodness.

The development and growth of the child is a process that proceeds without interruption. During this period, we observe the development of his formation as a person, his desire, interest and feelings to first realize the universe through the material around him and find meaning in him. It is known that each child is unique in his nature, talent, ability, interests and opportunities. None of them repeat the other exactly.

Each period of life, according to the characteristics and needs of development, has its own specific stages. This is what the preschool age period falls into when a child grows up. Children are considered to be a melodious universe and live in a very rapid growth, development and transformation. We can see how significant this very circuit is in raising children. The goal of the formation of the personality of the child in the preschool educational organization and the family is healthy and mature, while preparing for school education and life. Indeed, the earlier education begins, the earlier its effect is manifested and has a positive effect on the entire way of life of a person.

As we all know, younger children love to hear fairy tales and stories. Children learn by hearing small –scale works of art belonging to the genre of the story, summarizing the events that can be experienced in people's lives, as well as important

aspects of life. In stories, usually an episode in a person's life is taken as an image object. The essence of the stories is more vital in relation to the abstraction in fairy tales. Both the content and the form of the story are considered a suitable genre for children of preschool age. Because, when children reach the age of five, six, their interest in real i.e. accurate information in stories wakes up.

Although children of preschool age are interested in the behavior of blue heroes, appearance, portrait image, stories about events, they also like to compose or hear stories based on pace. To do this, it is advisable to work with children from an early age in the family and in the educational organization, with samples of Fine Arts. In fine arts classes in kindergartens, the little ones are given their initial understanding of the laws of nature and society, the secrets of Man and the universe, their shape, structure, color originality and interconnection. And this forms and develops in children the views of the materialistic world from youth. In preschool education, when purposefully enriching children's speech, it is appropriate to rely on the initial knowledge that children receive in fine art classes.

Based on the pace, it is possible to positively influence the development of children, both mentally and mentally, by directing them to independent reflection, to penetrate into the essence of works of art, to discover the character traits of the described heroes, along with the development of their oral speech. This in turn requires certain training from both the educator and the children. To do this, it is necessary to ensure sufficient vocabulary in children, to be able to think independently and logically connect their thoughts, and to be formed the skill of articulating in consistency. It also has a positive effect to inform children about colors and their functions so that they can compose a story based on it to see the colorful pace. When these works are taught both by parents and family members in the family, the skills of expressing opinions on the basis of pictures in children increase even more. As the child meditates on the picture, how the moment reflected in it is expressed in the image, he perceives as such and expresses in words what he sees. This situation limits to some extent the small story that the child has made based on the picture. If a child is taught in an image statement to clarify the unity of space, time, and time, it allows them to improve their skills of independent thinking, substantiating their views.

Drawing up a story based on pictures reveals his thinking in a child at the same time his independent thinking, his personal world, spiritual appearance. In the process of teaching children to compose a small story based on a picture, it is advisable to carry out the following stages in order to form and develop their independent thinking and their image skills. To develop children's imagination and independent statement about logical reasoning and reasoning based on pictures, about the situation in the picture and how to react to it, and about the continuation of the image. The work carried out at such

a stage will expand the range of observation in children and the vision and image of the world.

Preschool children love to watch the pace and make lively and interesting stories about them. And this forms in children the skill to express what they see at a pace, their imagination to others. Children begin to have an increased interest in the pace in this process. The pace reminds them of what they see or what they are involved in and the events. Throws his imagination out of balance. Another important aspect of teaching to compose a story based on pace is the manifestation in the child's imagination of events that are impossible to see, identifying and enriching his knowledge about them. Drawing up a story based on pace helps to form moral qualities in children.

When teaching children to tell stories by looking at a picture, subject drawings, plot drawings, reproductions, landscape and still life, etud paintings are used, which describe the content of an object. Through these pictures, children learn to compose stories that describe things-objects, story-visual stories, pictorial stories. Educators as well as parents should be guided by the following requirements when choosing a picture for storytelling; a) that the events are simple, b) that the children follow the principle of complicating the event according to their age, d) that they contribute to the development of the child's imagination, thinking, aesthetic feelings, observation, speech .

In place of the conclusion, it can be noted that by teaching children to tell stories based on pace, their speech is activated. On the basis of different pace, the skill of creating an independent story, expressing opinions develops. Learns to correctly understand the content of the pace. Love for nature increases. Keeps in memory for a long time the events and events that you see based on the pace. Based on what he sees, the skill of creating verbal text is formed. They will have the qualifications to give a personal attitude to the work.

List of used literature:

1. Q.Husanbayeva, M.Khazratkulova, G.Berdialiyeva. "Methodology for working with literary text in preschool education. –Tashkent innovation-Zia. pages 260-265, 2020.
2. M.Nurmatova. "Methodology of making and pictorial activity of painting" – Tashkent; 2010. Pages 3-6.
3. Q.Shodiyeva. "Style of speech theory". 2009. 220-230 pages.
4. O.Sadikova, D.Toshboyeva. "Children's psychology publisher". –Tashkent; 2013. 243-248 pages.